

Original Article

UTILIZATION OF INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGIES FOR ENHANCEMENT OF BUSINESS BANKING OF FIRST BANK ENUGU IN THE DIGITAL WORLD

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Abstract

This study examined the use of information and communication technologies (ICT) to improve business banking at First Bank Enugu in the digital age. Three research questions directed the study. The chosen research design was a survey. The study population included 270 staff members across six (6) First Bank branches in Enugu Metropolis. A simple random sampling method was used to select 100 staff members as respondents. The sampling approach involved balloting without replacement. The data collection instrument was a questionnaire titled "Utilization of ICTs for Enhancement of Business Banking in the Digital World" (UICTEBBDW). Mean scores were used for data analysis. Findings indicated that ICT utilization has improved the efficiency of banking operations and customer satisfaction at First Bank Plc in Enugu Metropolis. The results also identified some challenges associated with ICT use in enhancing business banking at First Bank Plc. The study recommends increasing the use of various ICT channels in business banking across all Nigerian commercial banks, especially for self-services such as ATM requests, cheque books, account updates, and statement requests. Customers should familiarize themselves with all the ICT channels available and use them appropriately. Banks must also prioritize cybersecurity, ensuring all internet channels are secure and protected. Protecting customer data is crucial to preventing hackers from accessing and compromising accounts.

Keywords: Utilization; Information and Communication Technology; Enhancement; Business banking; digital world

INTRODUCTION

Today's business environment is highly dynamic, experiencing rapid transformations driven by technological innovation, increasing awareness, and evolving customer demands. Business organizations, particularly those in the banking industry of the 21st century, operate within a technologically driven environment marked by rapid and unpredictable changes (James, 2010). No business without technology can break even. Information and communication technology (ICT) is at the center of global change.

The demand for efficiency and effectiveness in how banks operate as leading players in a nation's financial sector often drives a desire for improved technologies (Binugo & Aregbeshola, 2014). Before the advent of information and communication technology, conducting business, especially in banks, was difficult and stressful. Banks used manual methods for account opening and documentation. As a result, customers often queued for hours before being attended to. Furthermore, delayed responses from customer service frequently resulted in substantial losses for customers. Moreover, customers were limited to visiting bank branches where they opened accounts because

banks could not share or transfer data. Many people, including businesses, find it cumbersome to visit banks for transactions.

Thus, the low productivity, profitability, and efficiency of many Nigerian banks necessitate the introduction of information technology to address the challenges of the present-day banking system. The banking industry is one of the critical sectors of the economy whose contribution to the pace of development and economic growth cannot be fully quantified. Changes in today's digital world revealed the importance of ICT in equipping the banking sector to fully grapple with the exigencies of global competition (Madueme, 2015).

Information and Communication Technology (ICT)

Enomate and Audu (2022), citing Standish Group (2006), opine that Information and Communication Technology refers to a wide range of computerized technologies that enable communication and the electronic capturing, processing, and transmission of information, allowing the industries to develop and maintain a competitive edge in the global market to practice their services to rejuvenate the innovative trends. In line with this definition, ICT refers to the technologically driven integration of tools and resources designed to transmit, produce, store, retrieve, and share information among intended users.

According to Shokeen et al. (2022), Information and Communication Technology (ICT) refers to technologies that enable access to information through telecommunications. In line with this definition, Information and Communication Technology can be broken down into activities involving gathering, processing, or analyzing, storing or managing, and presenting or reporting data. Therefore, the adoption of ICT facilities in Nigeria's banking sector includes internet services, email, instant messaging platforms, and video conferencing tools that enhance communication among employees, customers, and other stakeholders. Other examples encompass telecommunication products, such as various types of telephones, modems, and electronic cables, information kiosks and transaction machines, World Wide Web sites, multimedia, and office equipment, including copiers, laptops, desktops, fax machines, and robots (Ado & Kawugana, 2024).

ICT impacts banking operations by simplifying customer inquiries, reducing transaction time, and enhancing service delivery. In recent decades, commercial banks have increasingly invested in information technology (IT) to streamline their operations, enhance competitiveness, and improve the range and quality of services they offer. According to Ukah (2013), the Nigerian banking industry has become highly ICT-based and is reaping the benefits of a technological revolution, as evidenced by its implementation in most of its operations. Many commercial banks are making huge investments in technology to maintain and upgrade their infrastructure, in order not only to provide new electronic information-based services, but also to take timely advantage of new off-the-shelf electronic services such as online retail banking, which is making it possible for very small institutions to take advantage of new technologies at quite reasonable costs. These developments may ultimately change the competitive landscape in the financial services market.

Information and Communication Technology (ICT) facilitates the networking of commercial bank branches and other banks within and outside the nation. Computerization and inter-connection of geographically scattered stand-alone bank branches and other banks at national and global levels into one unified system in the form of a wide area network (WAN) or enterprise network (EN) for the creation and sharing of consolidated customer information or records. It enables faster inter-branch transactions by eliminating the barriers of distance and time. Hence, there is more productivity per time period. Additionally, as multiple networked branches operate as a unified system, a virtual division of labor develops among them, leading to greater operational efficiency and productivity. Furthermore, the information-sharing infrastructure established by banks reduces customers' need to travel to branch locations, thereby allowing them more time for productive activities.

Binugo and Aregbeshola (2014) assert that advancements in technology have led to the emergence of information and communication technology (ICT), resulting in significant transformations in the way businesses operate in the modern era. Information and communication technology refers to the various technologies that enhance the creation, storage, processing, communication, and dissemination of information. It involves the different infrastructure used in these processes.

In the bid to catch up with global developments and improve the quality of their service delivery, Nigerian banks have invested much in ICTs, widely adopted electronic and telecommunication networks for delivering a wide range of value-added products and services (Ado & Kawugana, 2024), and in the last few years, have transformed from manual to digital systems.

Oxford Advanced Learner's Dictionary defined the word "utilization" as "the action of making practical and effective use of something." On the other hand, it defined advancement as "an increase or improvement in quality, value, or extent". The Cambridge dictionary defines enhancement as the process of improving the quality, amount, or strength of something. As such, the study ascertained how First Bank Plc utilized ICT to enhance business banking.

Afunkoyo (2023) study examined how the adoption of information technology affected the operations of commercial banks and the effects of information technology on banks and customer relationships. The study reviewed that information technology has tremendously improved the growth and performance of Nigerian commercial banks.

Ado and Kawugana (2024) examined the Impact of Electronic Banking on Customer Service Delivery in Deposit Money Banks, finding revealed that Internet banking, mobile banking, Electronic banking, and Automated Teller Machines (ATMs) have positively and significantly impacted effective customer service delivery in Nigerian deposit Money Banks.

Adekunle and Rafiu (2014) studied the contribution of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) to the performance of the South African banking industry. The study found that the use of ICT increases the Return on Capital Employed (ROCE) together with the Return on Assets (ROA) of the South African banking industry.

Luka and Frank (2012), in their work titled "The impact of ICTs on banks: A Case study of the Nigerian Banking Industry," indicated that investment in the ICT system and infrastructures has become a key element in productivity and growth in the banking industry.

Nwakoby, Sidi, and Ofobruku (2018) examined the impact of information and communication technology on the performance of deposit money banks in Nigeria and found that ICT has greatly influenced the quality of banking operations, performance, and return on equity.

Oyinkola (2018) conducted a study on the impact of Information Technology on banking operations in the First Bank of Nigeria PLC. The results revealed that IT has significantly enhanced the growth and performance of Nigerian commercial banks, leading to increased customer satisfaction.

Judith and Patrick (2016) reviewed the Influence of Innovations on The Performance of Commercial Banks in Nkuru Central Business District, Kenya, and concluded that bank innovations have a positive effect on the financial performance of the commercial banks in Kenya.

Business Banking

Business banking refers to banking services tailored for businesses, ranging from small-scale enterprises to large corporations, and involves products and services designed to help them manage their finances, cash flow, and growth. Business banking, according to Kagan (2020), is a company's financial dealings with an institution that provides business loans, credit, savings accounts, and checking accounts, specifically designed for companies

rather than for individuals. Business banking occurs when a bank, or a division of a bank, only deals with businesses.

A bank that primarily serves individual customers is referred to as a retail bank, whereas one that focuses on capital markets is known as an investment bank. Some banks deal with both types of clients. Therefore, business banking can be defined as the range of financial services a bank provides to businesses and corporations. Services offered under business banking include loans, credit facilities, savings accounts, and checking accounts, all specifically tailored to meet business needs. Banks can offer business, retail, and investment banking services under one roof (Kagan, 2020).

Digital World

The digital world is a vast and continually evolving concept that has advanced rapidly in recent years, yet still has considerable ground to cover before reaching a broader segment of the global population. The term “digital world” refers to the totality of circumstances that characterize the living conditions in the digital age, which will be significantly shaped by a multitude of digital technologies (Lengsfeld, 2023).

The term “digital world” highlights how digital technologies will fundamentally transform human living conditions in the information age, impacting them in pervasive and far-reaching ways. The concept of a “digital world” rest on the expectation that the systems and structures shaping life on Earth will not only be infused with digital technologies but ultimately dominated by them (Lengsfeld, 2023). The digital world has evolved significantly in recent decades with the rise of the Internet, social networks, and digital applications; however, progress remains uneven across sectors and societies worldwide.

First Bank and Utilization of ICT

First Bank of Nigeria Limited (FirstBank) is West Africa’s premier bank and has been Nigeria’s leading provider of financial inclusion services for over 127 years. With over 750 business locations and over 130,620 Banking Agents spread across 99% of the 774 Local Government Areas in Nigeria, FirstBank provides a comprehensive range of retail and corporate financial services to serve its over 30 million customers.

In the 2019 annual report, First Bank PLC reported that the department made a steady effort to effectively use ICT to improve the efficiency and quality of service delivery in the financial sector. Undoubtedly, ICT is transforming the global banking industry at a revolutionary pace. It is worth noting that extensive local and international research and development propel modern banking in Nigeria. It is an effort to establish the prevailing trend in the adoption of ICT in business banking of Nigerian commercial banks (Afunkoyo, 2023).

In 2022, First Bank of Nigeria Limited received two International Investor Awards— “Best Bank in Nigeria 2022” and “Best Bank in Digital Transformation Nigeria 2022”—in recognition of its ongoing efforts to reinvent its digital banking channels, as cited in First Bank Blog (2025).

Since its establishment in 1894, FirstBank has consistently nurtured strong customer relationships by upholding the principles of sound corporate governance, solid liquidity, effective risk management, and strategic leadership. Over the years, the Bank has led the financing of private investment in infrastructure development in the Nigerian economy by playing key roles in the Federal Government’s privatization and commercialization schemes.

With its global reach, FirstBank offers prospective investors seeking to explore Nigeria’s vast business opportunities a world-class, internationally competitive brand and a trusted financial partner, as cited in First Bank Blog (2025).

In today’s digital age, digital banking has become a convenient and fast way to manage your finances. Whether you are looking to open a new account or you want to make a major switch from in-branch banking to alternative

channels, there are many online options to suit customers' interests. One of the biggest advantages of digital banking is the ability to access your accounts on the go.

With mobile banking apps and online banking platforms, you can do almost all your banking transactions without visiting a branch. These include fund transfers, card requests, bill payments, account statement generation, loan applications, airtime purchases, complaints about failed transactions, and many more.

At First Bank, there are different digital banking options tailored for customer convenience. They are:

1. **Lit App by First Bank**
2. **FirstMobile App**
3. **Quick Response (QR) Payment Solution**
4. **FirstOnline**
5. **FirstBank USSD Banking (894#)**

While presenting a paper at the Future Banking Tech West Africa conference in Lagos, Dr. Sola Adeduntan, Group Managing Director and CEO of First Bank of Nigeria, noted that customers' banking behavior, attitudes, and expectations have evolved significantly over the years (Audu, 2024).

Audu (2024) also observed that today's bank customers are hyper-connected, well-informed, emotionally driven, and value-oriented. They are more willing to share personal information, place greater emphasis on enhanced experiences, and are prepared to pay more for quality services.

Purpose of the Study

The purpose of this study was to examine how information and communication technologies are utilized to enhance business banking at First Bank, Enugu, in the context of the digital era. Specifically, the study sought to:

1. Determine how the influence of information and communication technology (ICT) enhanced the smooth running of banking activities in First Bank Plc, Enugu Metropolis.
2. Determine how the influence of information and communication technology (ICT) enhanced customer satisfaction in First Bank Plc, Enugu Metropolis.
3. Ascertain if there are observable challenges with the utilization of ICT in the enhancement of business banking of First Bank Plc, Enugu Metropolis.

Research Questions

1. How has the influence of information and communication technology (ICT) enhanced the smooth running of banking activities in First Bank Plc, Enugu Metropolis?
2. How has the influence of information and communication technology (ICT) enhanced customer satisfaction in First Bank Plc, Enugu Metropolis?
3. What identifiable challenges are associated with the utilization of ICT in enhancing business banking at First Bank Plc., Enugu Metropolis?

Method

The research design adopted for this study was a survey design. This design was employed to gather diverse perspectives from people on a matter of broad interest. Survey design is a data collection method in which tools are used to collect information about a problem. Survey design enabled the author to elicit responses from a sampled population, which was used for generalization. The research was based on a population drawn from First Bank Plc, Enugu metropolis. The study population consists of 270 staff across six branches of First Bank Plc in Enugu Metropolis. A simple random sampling technique was used to select 100 staff as respondents for the study. The study employed random sampling through balloting without replacement to select the sample.

The instrument used for data collection was a questionnaire titled “utilization of ICTs for the enhancement of business banking in the digital world” (UICTEBBDW). The instrument was validated by three (3) experts in Enugu State University of Science and Technology (ESUT), Enugu. Two of the experts were from the Department of Business and Entrepreneurship Education, and the other one was from the Department of Mathematics and Computer Education. To assess the instrument’s reliability, the test-retest method was applied by administering the validated instrument to 20 staff members of First Bank Plc in Nsukka. The reliability of the instrument was established using Cronbach's Alpha, and a reliability coefficient of 0.78 was obtained, showing that the instrument is reliable.

RESULT

The analysis results were presented in alignment with the research questions.

Research Question 1

How has the influence of information and communication technology (ICT) enhanced the smooth running of banking activities in First Bank Plc, Enugu Metropolis?

Table 1: Mean rating on how the influence of ICT enhanced the smooth running of banking activities in First Bank Plc, Enugu Metropolis

s/no	Items	SA	A	D	SD	N	$\sum FX$	\bar{X}	Decision
1	ICT reduces long queues in the banking hall	50	20	15	15	100	305	3.00	Agree
2	It facilitates the transfer of money	70	15	10	5	100	350	3.50	Strongly Agree
3	It helps in the security of one’s account	60	25	10	5	100	340	3.40	Agree
4	It builds customer-staff relationships	65	15	12	8	100	337	3.37	Agree
5	It enables the easy opening of a bank account	55	25	15	5	100	330	3.30	Agree
6	It reduces risk in the banking hall	50	30	10	10	100	320	3.20	Agree
7	Helps in building of bank's database	57	30	10	3	100	341	3.41	Agree
Grand Mean								3.31	

Table 1 above shows the mean scores on the influence of ICT in enhancing the smooth running of the business banking of First Bank Plc, Enugu metropolis. All the items have mean scores ranging from 3.00-3.41, which is above the cut-off value of 2.50. This implies that the respondents agreed that ICT has a positive influence on the business banking activities of First Bank Plc, Enugu metropolis.

Research Question 2

How has information and communication technology (ICT) enhanced customer satisfaction in First Bank Plc, Enugu Metropolis?

Table 2: Mean rating on how information and communication technology (ICT) enhanced customer satisfaction in First Bank Plc, Enugu Metropolis

s/no	Items	SA	A	D	SD	N	$\sum FX$	\bar{X}	Decision
1	Customers are satisfied with the way ICT enables easy withdrawal of money via ATMs.	63	22	14	1	100	347	3.47	Strongly Agree
2	ICT helps in easy business transactions between the customer and the bank	70	15	10	5	100	350	3.50	Strongly Agree
3	Customers feel satisfied using the FirstMobile app to do transactions at home	51	33	16	-	100	335	3.35	Agree
4	Customers prefer using a POS to going to the bank	49	18	23	10	100	306	3.06	Agree
5	Customers are satisfied with the prompt services offered by ICTs.	17	61	19	3	100	292	2.92	Agree
6	Online customer service and internet self-service channels provide customer satisfaction	50	20	15	15	100	305	3.05	Agree
Grand Mean								3.22	

The analysis presented in Table 2 of this study shows that the utilization of information and communication technology (ICT) has significantly enhanced customer satisfaction at First Bank Plc, Enugu Metropolis. The mean rating of the respondents indicated that items 1 (3.47) and item 2 (3.50) strongly agreed with the research question. While items 3-6 (3.35, 3.06, 2.92, and 3.05) agreed respectively with the research question. Therefore, the grand mean of the responses (3.32) indicated that utilization of ICT influences customer satisfaction in First Bank Plc, Enugu Metropolis.

Research Question 3

Are there observable challenges with the utilization of ICT in the enhancement of business banking at First Bank Plc, Enugu Metropolis?

Table 3: Mean rating on observable challenges with the utilization of ICT in the enhancement of business banking of First Bank Plc, Enugu Metropolis

s/no	Items	SA	A	D	SD	N	$\sum FX$	\bar{X}	Decision
1	Electricity challenges	71	11	3	15	100	338	3.38	Agree
2	A telecommunication network that disrupts operations	81	3	9	7	100	358	3.58	Strongly Agree
3	Activities of internet fraudsters	69	24	7	-	100	362	3.62	Strongly Agree
4	Bank charges on internet services	5	15	40	40	100	185	1.85	Disagree
5	Software attacks by a virus	54	37	6	3	100	342	3.42	Agree

6	ATM/POS payment	debits	without	50	20	15	15	100	305	3.05	Agree
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Grand Mean										3.15
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In the analysis carried out in Table 3 of this study, it was found that there are observable challenges with the utilization of ICT in the enhancement of business banking of First Bank Plc, Enugu Metropolis. The mean rating of the respondents indicated that items 2 (3.58) and item 3 (3.62) strongly agreed with the research question. While items 1, 5, and 6 (3.38, 3.42, and 3.05) agreed respectively with the research question. However, item 4 (1.85) disagreed that bank charges constitute a challenge to the utilization of ICTs in First Bank plc. Thus, the grand mean of the responses (3.15) indicated that there are observable challenges with the utilization of ICT in the enhancement of business banking of First Bank Plc, Enugu Metropolis.

DISCUSSION OF FINDINGS

Based on the findings from research question 1, the utilization of information and communication technology (ICT) has enhanced the smooth running of banking activities in First Bank Plc, Enugu Metropolis. The analysis has a grand mean of 3.32. The study's findings support Binugo and Aregbeshola (2014), who contend that technological advancements have spurred the emergence of information and communication technology (ICT), profoundly reshaping modern business operations.

Information and communication technology refers to the various technologies that enhance the creation, storage, processing, communication, and dissemination of information. It involves the different infrastructure used in these processes. Additionally, Afunkoyo (2023) noted that ICT is transforming the global banking industry. It is important to note that extensive local and international research and development guide modern banking in Nigeria. It is an effort to establish the prevailing trend in the adoption of ICTs in the business banking of Nigerian commercial banks.

The analysis for research question 2 revealed that the use of information and communication technology (ICT) has significantly improved customer satisfaction at First Bank Plc, Enugu Metropolis. It has a mean rating of 3.32. The study's findings corroborate Woherem's (2010) assertion, cited in Afunkoyo (2023), that ICT adoption offers customers advantages such as banking from anywhere, banking at any time, and prolonged banking hours. These benefits provide comfort, convenience, and ease of use for bank transactions. Oyinkola (2018) also posits that ICT has greatly improved the growth and performance of Nigerian commercial banks and has led to increased customer satisfaction. Undoubtedly, ICT utilization in business banking has enabled the integration of operations across large banks with multiple branches nationwide, allowing transactions to be conducted at any branch within the centralized network without the customer being physically present.

The analysis for research question 3 revealed notable challenges linked to the use of ICT in improving business banking at First Bank Plc, Enugu Metropolis. The responses analyzed have a mean rating of 3.15. The study's findings align with Ado and Kawugana (2024), who reported that power outages during transactions create negative perceptions of e-banking and that inadequate regulation of e-banking infrastructure poses significant limitations for banking in Nigeria.

CONCLUSION

This study investigated how information and communication technologies are utilized to enhance business banking at First Bank Enugu in the digital era. The study became essential due to the significant impact of ICT across various sectors of the economy. The study examined how ICT has transformed business banking at First Bank Plc, focusing on its effect on the bank, its customers, and the challenges observed.

The utilization of ICT in business banking is transforming the way banks operate and do business in Nigeria. This has led to changes in trade volume and improved interconnectivity between banks. It has increased business transactions across local and international banks. ICT utilization has also sparked a transformation in the banking sector. It therefore requires substantial investment in ICT to provide a transaction and payment system that meets the demands of an electronically interconnected global business environment.

The utilization of various forms of ICT has greatly influenced the content and quality of banking operations and customer satisfaction.

This research has shown that through information and communication technology, First Bank Nigeria Plc is running a smooth banking business. Bank payments and other transactions have been simplified through self-service facilities, such as automated customer service machines, where prospective customers can complete their account opening documents online. It has enabled customers to verify their account numbers and receive guidance on when and how to collect their cheque books, credit and debit cards, and access POS services. The study concludes that the utilization of information and communication technologies has enhanced the business banking of First Bank Enugu in the digital world.

RECOMMENDATIONS

The following recommendations are proffered:

1. The utilization of various ICT channels in business banking should be enhanced in all commercial banks in Nigeria, especially for self-services such as the request of ATMs, cheque books, account updates, statement of accounts, etc. All commercial banks should strive to utilize ICT in their daily operations to enhance business in the digital world.
2. Bank customers should get themselves acquainted with all the ICT channels provided by their banks and use them appropriately. It will significantly reduce customer congestion in banks. Greater awareness should be raised to inform customers that many banking inquiries and requests can be completed via digital platforms rather than visiting bank branches. It will help to improve customer satisfaction.
3. Issues relating to cybersecurity must be taken seriously by all banks using ICT. The threat of internet fraudsters has continued to instil fear among customers.

All banks must ensure that all internet channels are properly secured and protected. Customer data must be securely protected to prevent hackers from accessing and compromising customer accounts.

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